

Thermogravimetric Study of Kinetic Parameters of Dehydroxylation of some Clay and other Minerals.

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Thermal decomposition (dehydroxylation) of clay minerals is of great importance because of its potential industrial applications. The kinetics were therefore studied thermogravimetrically and the energies of activation of the main steps in the decomposition of clay and a few other minerals were calculated by Dave & Chopra's method. The E values, thus obtained were found to agree well with those calculated from the differential thermal analysis curves.

MANY naturally occurring clay and non-clay minerals contain water of constitution which is lost on heating. Loss of this may take place in one or more stages and the temperature of each stage of dehydroxylation is characteristic of each mineral and continues until the reaction is over. Differential thermal studies of many minerals have been carried out by numerous workers¹⁻⁶. Recently some studies have been made using the thermogravimetric technique too⁷⁻¹⁰.

These minerals are put to various uses through processes, of which firing is an important step. It is, therefore, of importance to know their kinetics of decomposition, because a knowledge of their energies of activation and rates of decomposition etc. will be of immense use in any firing operations of these materials. The object of the present study was to obtain these data for indigenous materials, for which purpose the thermogravimetric technique has been utilised.

Experimental

Samples of kaolinite, nontronite, montmorillonite, bentonite, illite, gibbsite and bauxite were obtained from indigenous sources. Their source and chemical compositions are as shown in Table 1.

magnification ($\times 400$) for the purpose of identifying them. Further confirmations were made by obtaining X-ray diffraction patterns of the powder. The results confirmed the minerals in question; however, small amounts of impurities were indicated in certain cases.

The thermogravimetric analyses were carried out on a Stanton Thermogravimetric balance (model HT-M). One gram of the material was taken in each case. The heating rate was kept fixed at 3° per minute.

The differential thermal analyses were carried out manually by controlling the rate of heating at 10° per min through a variable transformer. The amount of the material taken in each case was 0.75 g. exactly. The differential temperature was recorded by a sensitive galvanometer.

Results and Discussion

The thermogravimetric, differential thermogravimetric and the differential thermal analysis curves for the different minerals are shown in Figs. 1-3.

The thermogravimetric curve for kaolinite (Fig. 1) shows a loss commencing at about 80°C. This loss, which can be seen in the D.T.G. curves, corresponds with the D.T.A. curve which shows an endotherm commencing at 75°. This loss obviously corresponds

TABLE 1—ORIGIN AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MATERIALS

Sl. No.	Material	Origin	Loss on ignition	SiO ₂ %	Fe ₂ O ₃ %	Al ₂ O ₃ %	CaO %	MgO %	K ₂ O + Na ₂ O
1.	Kaolinite	Chaibasa(Bihar)	11.70	42.67	3.40	38.50	2.05	0.90	0.50
2.	Nontronite	Rajasthan	17.00	51.20	1.50	22.14	3.72	0.00	4.20
3.	Illite	Rajasthan	11.90	55.20	4.00	16.51	6.92	1.81	3.21
4.	Montmorillonite	Saurashtra(Gujarat)	23.10	53.48	0.41	17.41	2.12	5.38	0.25
5.	Bentonite	Rajasthan	17.52	45.23	10.24	28.48	1.05	0.00	0.48
6.	Gibbsite	Jabalpur(M.P.)	25.23	3.88	12.53	58.30a	0.00	0.00	0.01
7.	Bauxite	Katni(M.P.)	25.08	5.31	5.21	64.32b	0.00	0.00	0.05

Includes TiO₂ a = 3.04; b = 4.12

The samples were ground lightly and fractions were collected between U.S. standard sieves No. 100 and 120. No residues were held and whole of the samples were ground and fractioned. The ground samples were then examined under a petrographic microscope at high

to the physically adsorbed water. Another loss in weight commences at 400°, and continues upto 735°. This is also shown in the D.T.A. curve by a stronger endotherm commencing at 400°. These changes obviously are due to the water of constitution in the mineral (11),

D.T.A. curve also shows another exothermic change starting at 850°. This is due to changes of structural nature and does not correspond to any change in weight.

In the case of nontronite the thermogravimetric curve (Fig. 1) shows loss starting at 65° and continuing upto about 460°. Another loss commences only a little later, at 480° and continues upto 660°; this means slight overlapping. These changes become much more distinctive in the D.T.G. curve. The D.T.A. curve also shows corresponding endothermic peaks. It also shows an exothermic change starting at 800° and extending beyond 1000°. This does not have any corresponding change in the T.G. and D.T.G. curves and denotes structural changes.

Fig. 1. Thermograms of Kaolinite, nontronite and illite

In the mineral illite the thermogravimetric curves (Fig. 1) show the loss starting at 40° to complete at 330°. The corresponding D.T.A. peak extends over 60-180° and both the peaks are sharp and strong. Two other losses in the region 500°-740° and 770°-920° are slow and hence denote slower decomposition. The D.T.A. peaks of medium intensity extend over 430°-700° and 720°-820°. The D.T.A. also has an exothermic peak in continuation of the last endotherm (820°-1000°)

The loss starts early in the case of montmorillonite, the thermogravimetric curve (Fig. 2) shows it at 50°,

the D.T.G. endothermic peak starting at 60°. There is another, comparatively less, loss in weight starting at 600° and continuing upto 800°. This corresponds to two separate low intensity endothermic peaks starting at 470° and 770°. There is another strong exothermic peak (870°-1090°) coinciding with structural changes in the material.

In the mineral bentonite loss starts at about the room temperature. This continues upto 250° in thermogravimetric curve (Fig. 2). The corresponding endotherm in the D.T.A. curve is medium in intensity. The thermogram shows another endotherm between 245°-290°. Another endothermic change starts at 430° and continues upto 680°. The corresponding thermogravimetric loss starts a little early, at 420°. The D.T.A.

Fig. 2. Thermograms of Montmorillonite and Bentonite

curve also shows an exothermic change starting at 760° and ending at 830°.

The minerals gibbsite and bauxite are not clay minerals. But they are associated with clay minerals in many cases and have wide occurrence. Because of these reasons they were included in this study. The thermogravimetric curve (Fig. 3) for gibbsite shows the loss to start at 207° to continue upto 480°, the D.T.A. curve denotes this change, obviously due to the loss of structural water, with a very sharp peak. The corresponding D.T.A. peak also ranges from 210°

460° and is fairly similar in nature to D.T.G. curve. Another instalment of loss takes place between 480° and 640°. This corresponds with a low intensity D.T.A. peak over 475°- 629° region.

The thermogravimetric curves (Fig. 3) for bauxite show an early loss between 120° and 170°, obviously due to the expulsion of physically absorbed water. The corresponding D.T.A. curve starts a little early (75°) but continues upto 160° and is characterised by a peak of very low intensity. The main loss takes place between the temperature of 175°-500° but tails off and ends around 650°. This corresponds in D.T.A. with a sharp endotherm between 145°-450°. There is another endotherm of very low intensity (460°-530°). These portions appear to be because of the difficultly-expelled last traces of water.

Fig. 3. Thermograms of Bauxite and Gibbsite

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the above observations, in general, it can be said that the losses in weight, recorded by the thermogravimetric curves, due to the dehydroxylation of the minerals, correspond with the main characteristic endotherm of the mineral on the D.T.A. curve. The shifts in the curves are mainly due to the inherent nature of the techniques; whereas in the D.T.A. the temperature measuring device is inserted inside the sample, in the thermogravimetric measurements it is kept outside the crucible in the furnace chambers. Moreover the heating rates employed in the two cases are different and this is bound to affect the threshold decomposition temperatures as well as the shapes of the curves^{1,2}.

Making use of the D.T.G. curves the activation energies of the dehydration were calculated from the equation^{1,3}.

$$K = \frac{(A/m_0)^{n-1} (-dx/dt)}{(A-a)^n}$$

where 'K' is the specific rate constant.
 'A' is the total area under the differential thermogravimetric curve for any reaction.
 'm₀' is the initial mole-fraction of the reactant
 'a' is the area for the reaction upto time 't'.
 dx/dt is the height of the curve at time 't'
 and 'n' is the order of the reaction with respect to the reactant.

As already observed by Murray and White¹⁴ and subsequently confirmed by Allison¹⁵, Vaughan¹⁶ and Kissinger¹⁷ the dehydroxylation of loose powdered minerals of this type can be regarded as a chemical reaction belonging to the first-order type. Hence a simplified version of the equation^{1,3} viz :

$$K = \frac{\left(\frac{-dx}{dt}\right)}{(A-a)}$$

can be used. The values of specific reaction rates at different temperatures (k) are then utilized through the Arrhenius' plots for the evaluation of the activation energies of the minerals. The values obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION ENERGIES OF THE MATERIALS

Sl. No.	Material	Threshold temperature (°C)		Activation Energy (Kcal/mole)	
		D.T.G.	D.T.G.	D.T.G.	D.T.A.
1.	Kaolinite	400	400	50.6	49.5
2.	Nontronite	65	50	26.0	28.4
3.	Illite	40	60	40.1	34.1
4.	Montmorillonite	60	60	35.3	35.7
5.	Bentonite	420	430	42.0	47.96
6.	Gibbsite	267	210	37.5	30.9
7.	Bauxite	170	120	28.7	28.1

Borchardt and Daniels^{1,8} model for the determination of kinetics from the D.T.A. data has been extended by Wendlandt^{1,9} Padmanabhan and Saraiya^{2,0}, Agarwala and Naik^{2,1} etc. to materials of this nature. Activation energies were calculated on this basis too and the values are reported in Table 2. Considerable agreement between the two sets of values, in spite of slight variations in the temperature ranges over which dehydroxylation took place, is obvious and underlines the correct order of the values.

The specimens taken for this study were naturally occurring materials and hence may not be absolutely pure. The impurities present may affect the activation energies to certain extent. However, these effects are

expected to be only slight and insignificant compared to the order of uncertainties normally obtained in the values of the kinetic parameters^{2,2}. Further work, however, is being taken up.

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References

1. R. C. MACKENZIE, *Geol. Foren. i stockholm Forth.*, 1956, 78, 508, (DTA of Clays, Central Press Aberdeen Scotland 1957).
2. W. J. SMOTHERS and Y. CHIANG, "DTA, Theory and Practice", Chem. Pub. Co. N. Y. 1958.
3. T. PETERS., *Schweiz Mineral Petrog. Mitt.* 1961, 41, 71.
4. M. S. N. RAO and M. R. A. RAO., *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1954, 36A, 227.
5. H. W. VEN DER MAREL., *Amer. Mineralogist*, 1956, 41, 222.
6. G. A. COLLINS and A. G. SWAN., *Trans. Canad Inst. Mining Met. i 57 (in Canad Mining Met. Bull.*, 1954, 508, 533 ; J. ADHIKARI., *J. Ind. Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1953, 6, 147 ; *Indian J. App. Chem.*, 1958, 21, 49.
7. I. HOFFMAN, M. SCHNITZER and J. R. WRIGHT., *Chem. Ind.*, London 1958, 261.
8. L. ERDEY, F. PAULIK and J. PAULIK., *Nature*, 1954, 174, 885.
9. M. SCHNITZER, J. R. WRIGHT and I. HOFFMAN., *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 440
10. D. STANAGILOVIC., *Vesmik Zavod geol, geophys. istrash Serbia.*, 1954, 11, 253.
11. W. F. BRADLEY and R. E. GRIM., *J. Phys. & Colloid Chem.*, 1948, 52, 1404 ; R. D. HULL., *Trans. Brit Ceram. Soc.*, 1953, 52, 589 ; W. F. COLE., *Nature*, 1955, 175, 384.
12. W. W. WENDLANDT, "Thermal Methods of Analysis", Interscience Publications N. Y. 1964, p. 179.
13. N. G. DAVE and S. K. CHOPRA., *Zeit Physical Chem.*, 1966, 48, 257.
14. P. MURRAY and J. WHITE., *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1949, 48, 187; 1955, 54, 137, 155, 204, *Clay Minerals Bull.* 1955, 2, 255.
15. E. S. ALLISON., *Clay Minerals Bull.*, 1955, 2, 242.
16. F. VAUGHAN., *Clay Minerals Bull.*, 1955, 2, 265.
17. H. E. KISSINGER., *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Standards*, 1956, 57, 217.
18. H. J. BORCHARDT and F. DANIELS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 41.
19. W. W. WENDLANDT., *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, 38, 571.
20. V. M. PADMANABHAN, S. C. SARAIYA and A. K. SUNDARAM., *J. Inorg. and Nuclear Chem.*, 1960, 12, 356.
21. R. P. AGARWALA and M. C. NAIK., *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1961, 24, 128.
22. S. W. BENSON., "The Foundation of Chemical Kinetics", McGraw Hill Book Co., Inc. Toronto, 1960, p. 92 and 316.